

Synthesis and characterization of copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes with a Schiff base derived from 3-formylsalicylic acid and thiocarbohydrazide

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Abstract : A series of mono and dinuclear complexes of the type $\text{Na}_2[\text{M}\{(3\text{-fsa})_2\text{-TCH}\}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]m\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{M}_2\{(3\text{-fsa})_2\text{-TCH}\}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]m\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $(3\text{-fsaH}_2)_2\text{-TCH}$ is a Schiff base derived from 3-formyl salicylic acid and thiocarbohydrazide, $n, m = 0, 1, 2$ and $\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Ni^{II} have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, thermal analysis, molar conductivity, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral data. The results indicate that the mononuclear Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are square planar; where as the mononuclear Co^{II} complex is tetragonal pyramidal with water molecules at the apical position. Antiferromagnetic spin exchange in dinuclear Cu^{II} complexes, subnormal magnetic moment values in dinuclear Ni^{II} complexes and existence of mixed spin state of dinuclear Co^{II} complexes comprising of a high and low spin Co^{II} ion have been established. The fungi toxicities of the complexes against some fungal pathogens have been studied.

Keywords : Schiff base, copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II).

The Schiffs base derived from 3-formyl salicylic acid (3-fsaH₂) and diamines and carbohydrazide have been widely used in the preparation of mononuclear and homo dinuclear complexes, hetero dinuclear complexes, and mixed spin complexes¹⁻⁵. As a part of our continuing investigation on the coordination chemistry of multidentate ligand containing NOS donors^{6,7}. We report here synthesis and characterization of hitherto unknown some mono and dinuclear metal complexes with a Schiff base derived from 3-formyl salicylic acid (3-fsaH₂) and thiocarbohydrazide.

Results and discussion

The complexes were formulated from the analytical data and molar conductance data support the suggested formulae (Table 1). The complexes are highly colored and sparingly soluble in common organic solvent but are soluble in DMSO and DMF. They are highly stable under normal condition and all of them decompose above 250 °C. The molar conductance data values (in DMSO) indicate the mononuclear complexes to be 2 : 1 electrolyte and dinuclear complexes to be non electrolyte in nature.

IR spectra : As the Schiff base ligand could not be isolated, the spectra of the complexes were compared with spectra of the starting materials and other related compounds. The bands observed in the spectra of metal

complexes at ~3300, ~1450, ~1320, ~1080, ~840 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and thioimide I, II, III and IV bands respectively of TCH skeleton⁸. All the above bands appear nearly the same position as found in the free TCH implying non-coordination of thioimide sulphur or nitrogen atom to the metal ion. The appearance of band at 1640 and 1460 cm⁻¹ in mononuclear complexes and their shifting to lower frequency 1605 and 1345 cm⁻¹ in dinuclear series indicates that the carboxylate group of salicylic acid moiety is free in mononuclear complexes but monodentate in dinuclear complexes⁹ as evidenced from the separation of $\Delta\nu_{\text{COO}} = \sim 260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The absence of band at ~3350 cm⁻¹ due to phenolic ν_{OH} and appearance of a band at 1500 cm⁻¹ instead of 1280 cm⁻¹ due to phenolic $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ of salicylic acid moiety and appearance of another band at 1630 cm⁻¹ at comparatively lower frequency region than usually free $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ value¹⁰ lead us to suggest that phenolic oxygen atom after deprotonation and azomethaine nitrogen atom have taken part in complexation as evidenced from the appearance of bands in the region 530-515 cm⁻¹ and 460-450 cm⁻¹ assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively¹¹.

However a broad band at ~3450 cm⁻¹ is observed in all the complexes indicating the presence of lattice/coordinated water molecules as confirmed by thermal analysis.

Thermal analysis : In mononuclear complexes weight loss was encountered at ~ 80 °C with a broad endothermic peak at the same temperature corresponding to two and one molecules of water of crystallization^{12,13} for copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes respectively. However, the first weight loss corresponding to loss of one molecule of water for mononuclear cobalt(II) complex occurred at 130 °C supported by an exothermic peak at the same temperature is the characteristic of coordinated water.

The thermogram of the dinuclear complexes exhibited the characteristics of coordinated water as well as water of crystallization. The loss of water of crystallization ranged from 60–80 °C corresponding to two and three molecules of water of crystallization for copper(II) and nickel(II) respectively. The elimination of coordinated water for copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes occurred in single step as supported by an endothermic peak at 130 °C and 140 °C respectively. Simultaneous elimination of coordinated water suggests them to be in the same chemical environment¹⁴. However the dinuclear cobalt(II) complex lost water molecules in two steps, one at 130 °C corresponding to the loss of one molecule of coordinated water (exactly at the same temperature as the mononuclear cobalt(II) complex) and the other at 145 °C corresponding to the loss of two molecules of coordinated water. Both the mono and dinuclear complexes finally decompose to their metal oxides.

Electronic spectra and magnetic properties :

Mononuclear complexes : The mononuclear copper(II) complex is paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.82$ B.M.) where as the nickel(II) complex is diamagnetic showing electronic spectral band at ~ 17150 and ~ 18550 cm^{-1} respectively indicating their geometry to be square planar¹⁵. The room temperature μ_{eff} value of cobalt(II) complex is 1.92 B.M. exhibiting electronic spectral band at ~ 9500 , ~ 13900 and ~ 16300 cm^{-1} indicating the cobalt(II) ion is low spin state having a tetragonal pyramidal environment¹⁶.

Dinuclear complexes : The room temperature μ_{eff} value of dinuclear copper(II) complex is 0.79 B.M. The reflectance spectrum of this complex exhibits two bands at ~ 17820 and ~ 15240 cm^{-1} . The higher energy band is tentatively assigned to the inner $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-N}_2\text{O}_2$ chromophore. The blue shift is quite indicative of enhancement of coplanarity during the formation of dinuclear complex involving antiferromagnetic spin interaction as suggested from magnetic moment value. The lower energy band ~ 15240 cm^{-1} is tentatively assigned to the outer $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-O}_4$ chromophore on an approximately octahedral environ-

ment with two water molecules in apical positions.

The dinuclear nickel(II) complex exhibits two additional bands at ~ 10000 and ~ 14940 cm^{-1} , besides the band at 18550 cm^{-1} . The former two bands are indicative of an outer $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-O}_4$ chromophore in an approximately octahedral environment due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ with two water molecule in apical positions, while the other band is due to a square planar $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-N}_2\text{O}_2$ chromophore. The position of this band remains same as that of mononuclear nickel(II) complex. However the magnetic moment value of this complex is (2.29 B.M.) being lower than the spin-only value indicating the formation of a dinuclear nickel(II) complex with one diamagnetic and one paramagnetic centre with weak antiferromagnetic spin pairing as evidenced from its electronic spectral data.

The electronic spectrum of $[\text{Co}_2\{(3\text{-fsaH}_2)_2\text{-TCH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\}]$ exhibits additional band at ~ 18400 cm^{-1} besides bands at ~ 9500 , ~ 12400 , ~ 16300 as observed for mononuclear cobalt(II) complexes. This band is indicative of an outer octahedral $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{-O}_4$ chromophore assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ in an approximately octahedral environment with two water molecule in apical positions; the band due to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ being merged with ~ 9500 cm^{-1} as marked it from its broadness. The magnetic moment of this complex had been found to be 4.9 B.M. in room temperature. The magnetic moment expected for high spin dinuclear cobalt(II), mixed (high spin and low spin) dinuclear cobalt(II) and low spin dinuclear cobalt(II) complexes are in the range of ~ 6.1 to ~ 4.7 , ~ 4.7 to ~ 5.9 , 2.7 to 4.00 B.M. respectively provided that no spin exchange interaction in operating between the cobalt(II) ions¹⁷. The magnetic moment values of this complex indicate it to be mixed spin dinuclear as supported by its electronic spectrum.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Based on the foregoing observation, the following tentative structure may be proposed for the complexes.

Experimental

All the chemical used were of A.R. grade. Solvent were used as supplied without further purification.

Preparation of 3-formylsalicylic acid (3-fsaH₂): 3-fsaH₂ was prepared by following the literature method of Duff and Bills¹⁸.

Preparation of thiocarbohydrazide (TCH): TCH was prepared according to the literature method of Audrieth *et al.*¹⁹. As the Schiff base ligand isolation proved futile, both mono and dinuclear complexes were prepared *in situ* by taking different amount of metal salts while keeping the 3-fsaH₂ and thiocarbohydrazide stoichiometric constant.

Preparation of mononuclear complexes :

An aqueous solution of hydrated metal(II) acetate (1 mmol) was added to an aqueous mixture (30 mL) of sodium carbonate (1 mmol), (3-fsaH₂)₂ (2 mmol) and thiocarbohydrazide (1 mmol). The resultant solution was refluxed on a water bath for about 1 h, during which micro-crystalline solid slowly separated out. It was thoroughly washed with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. The mononuclear complexes of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) were prepared in a similar method.

Preparation of dinuclear complexes :

The complexes were prepared by identical method as described above by taking 2 mmol of metal(II) acetate instead of 1 mmol.

The metal contents in the complexes have been determined by standard method²⁰. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the complexes were estimated by using a MLW-CHN microanalyzer. The analytical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1. Infrared spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Cary 2390 spectrophotometer. Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method²¹. The thermogravimetric analysis was done by Netzsch-429 thermoanalyzer simultaneous recording of TG and DT, curves at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in air. Around 50 to 100 mg of the sample was used in each case.

Fungicidal screening :

The antifungal activity of the complexes was tested

Table 1. Analytical data of complexes

Compd.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
		Metal	C	N	S	H
Na ₂ [Cu{(3-fsa) ₂ -TCH}].2H ₂ O	Brown	11.68 (11.73)	37.53 (37.62)	10.30 (10.39)	5.88 (6.21)	2.57 (2.61)
Na ₂ [Ni{(3-fsa) ₂ -TCH}].H ₂ O	Green	11.27 (11.33)	39.17 (39.24)	10.75 (10.83)	6.14 (6.53)	2.31 (2.36)
Na ₂ [Co{(3-fsa) ₂ -TCH}.H ₂ O]	Green	11.31 (11.73)	39.16 (39.28)	10.69 (10.78)	6.14 (6.37)	2.32 (2.39)
[Cu ₂ {(3-fsa) ₂ -TCH}.(H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O	Grey	21.21 (21.26)	34.17 (34.33)	9.38 (9.45)	5.36 (5.58)	3.01 (3.18)
[Ni ₂ {(3-fsa) ₂ -TCH}.(H ₂ O) ₂].3H ₂ O	Ivory	19.45 (19.59)	33.67 (34.03)	9.24 (9.45)	5.28 (5.58)	3.32 (3.45)
[Co ₂ {(3-fsa) ₂ -TCH}.(H ₂ O) ₃]	Grey	20.16 (20.69)	35.82 (36.24)	9.83 (10.11)	5.61 (5.88)	2.84 (3.01)

Table 2. Fungitoxicity of the copper(II), nickel(II) and cobalt(II) complexes against the fungal pathogens *Helminthosporium oryzae* and *Fusarium oxysporium*

Complexes	<i>Helminthosporium oryzae</i>					<i>Fusarium oxysporium</i>				
	% of inhibition over control					% of inhibition over control				
	100	200	400	800	1000	100	200	400	800	1000
Mononuclear copper(II)	13.1	18.9	25.4	60.2	69.2	12.5	17.6	25.5	55.4	66.2
Mononuclear nickel(II)	9.2	13.4	16.4	31.3	52.4	7.1	12.2	15.2	28.7	50.4
Mononuclear cobalt(II)	10.7	15.6	22.3	39.4	50.4	12.8	17.1	26.0	43.2	55.2
Dinuclear copper(II)	18.9	25.8	33.2	65.1	77.1	17.2	25.1	32.2	64.3	75.0
Dinuclear nickel(II)	13.5	15.7	19.7	34.2	56.8	15.7	19.2	22.3	42.7	62.4
Dinuclear cobalt(II)	15.2	20.1	25.5	42.3	60.2	13.3	16.8	23.5	41.3	58.2

against the organism *Fusarium* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* by the method of Horsfall²². The evaluation was carried out at 1000 ppm in dioxane. The amount of germination or growth inhibition was determined after inoculation of fungal spores to Czapek-dox agar media and also to the media containing the test sample and keeping in an incubator for 5 days. The % of inhibition was calculated as % of inhibition = $100(P - Q)/P$, where Q = area of colony growth with test sample, P = area of colony growth without test sample. The results obtained have been presented in the Table 2.

Transition metal chlorides, sulphates and nitrate can not be used as fungicides, as they cause damage to the leaves²³. However when applied as coordination compound they do little damage. The coordination compounds in the present investigation are expected to serve as fungicides without causing any plant damage. The fungicidal activities both for mononuclear complexes and dinuclear complexes is in the ordered $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$. Between the two series mono and dinuclear, the dinuclear species exhibits more fungitoxicity than the corresponding mononuclear species. This is quite obvious because of the higher concentration of the metal ions in the dinuclear complexes.

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